

METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMPROVING CREATIVE SKILLS OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER MEDICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract. This article highlights the importance of interactive methods in improving the creative abilities of future doctors studying at a higher medical educational institution, preparing them for creative professional activity.

In the article, the innovative technologies widely used in teaching modern students help to improve the teamwork skills and communicative competence of future teachers, as well as their ability to act independently in innovative pedagogical technologies.

Keywords: creativity, ability, creative ability, ability, innovative methods and approaches, pedagogical technologies, creative thinking, pedagogical cooperation, student, teacher, educational-cognitive activity, professional education, teamwork, training situations, enter the dialogue.

МЕТОДЫ И ТЕХНОЛОГИИ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКИХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ СТУДЕНТОВ ВЫСШИХ МЕДИЦИНСКИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ

Аннотация. В данной статье освещается значение интерактивных методов в совершенствовании творческих способностей будущих врачей, обучающихся в высшем медицинском образовательном учреждении, подготовке их к творческой профессиональной деятельности.

В статье инновационные технологии, широко используемые в обучении современных студентов, способствуют совершенствованию навыков работы в команде и коммуникативной компетентности будущих учителей, а также их способности действовать самостоятельно в инновационных педагогических технологиях.

Ключевые слова: креативность, способность, творческая способность, способность, инновационные методы и подходы, педагогические технологии, творческое мышление, педагогическое сотрудничество, студент, педагог, учебно-познавательная деятельность, профессиональное образование, коллективная работа, учебные ситуации, вступление в диалог.

In today's process of globalization, the development of modern technologies depends primarily on the intellectual potential of society, including the development of the education sector. Issues of the content and quality of education are considered a priority in society. In the developed and developing countries of the world, special attention is paid to the technology of education. Ways to improve education and increase its effectiveness are being sought, as well as the introduction of pedagogical technologies has become the focus of reforms in the field of education.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" provides for "development and implementation of author's programs within the educational programs of pedagogues, development of teaching methodology, as well as the use of relevant academic subjects, courses, modules, it was emphasized that they have the right to show creative activity. [1]

Creativity describes a person as a whole or his specific features, mental sharpness. Also, creativity is reflected as an important factor of talent. A teacher does not become a creator by himself. His creative ability is formed by consistently studying and working on himself over a period of time.

The qualities of creativity and creativity occupy a high place in the rating of skills and qualities required of a specialist. Today's pace of development requires every country and its citizens to constantly strive for innovation, new ideas, initiatives, unexpected approaches and solutions. A short-term break from this process or falling behind is bound to result in a significant backwardness, that is, dependence on advanced countries in all spheres.

On the other hand, today's doctors also need to keep up with the rapidly changing times and be a full participant in it. Because the legal documents and legal norms of the smart medical system are being approved in our Republic, and one is being replaced by another. In these processes, medical personnel can work practically in the systems of "smart medicine", "digital medicine" and effectively solve problems. That's right - in the new era of digitalization, only doctors with creative abilities will play a decisive role in our country's entry into the ranks of developed countries in the field of medicine.[2]

Today, activities aimed at creativity, creativity, and innovation are understood as creative activities.

The word "creativity" is derived from the word "create", meaning the ability of a person to be creative, the level of creativity, the individual's way of thinking that is far from conventionality or habit. , which characterizes the readiness to create fundamentally new ideas, as well as solving problems in a unique way, are creative abilities considered as an independent factor of talent [3, 42].

Ability is a unique combination of abilities that provides a person with the possibility of effective performance of this or that activity. Ability is a characteristic of a person's psychological and physiological structure. Ability improves in the process of acquisition of skills and competencies by a person. Any type of ability consists of a complex psychological concept of a person, which includes a system of characteristics proportional to the requirements of the activity. Therefore, ability should be understood not as a single characteristic, but as a synthesis of characteristics that can meet the requirements of a person's activity and provide an opportunity to achieve high performance in this activity.

The basic characteristic for all abilities is the ability to observe, that is, to understand a person, to be able to see one or another sign from an object, to distinguish. One of the leading features of the ability is to creatively imagine the essence of things and events.

The sensory organs and functional properties of the brain structure, which appear as the initial natural condition for the development of abilities, are called abilities. Talent is multifaceted. Different abilities can be developed on the basis of exactly the same abilities, depending on the nature of the requirements set by the person.

According to F.A. Gall, all human abilities, the qualities "intelligence" and "ability" have their special fixed centers in the cerebral hemispheres, that is, the level of development of these qualities is directly related to the amount of the corresponding parts of the brain. depends. Therefore, it is possible to determine the abilities of a person by simply looking at the skull or simply feeling the bumps on the head.

Abilities develop during professional activity. The first condition for the improvement of abilities is the cultivation of the need for activity. In order to educate the need for work, it is important to be interested in work and get used to it.

Abilities are closely connected with other qualities of a person. The fact that a person is talented depends to some extent on his mental processes, as well as the level of development of many mental characteristics. A high level of relevant cognitive processes plays a decisive role in the improvement of certain abilities.

For example, hearing is important for a musician, and visual perception is important for an artist. As long as a person is engaged in the improvement of his abilities, this development should not be an empty goal. The main task is to become a worthy and useful member of society.

Creative ability is a special ability of a teacher to learn new concepts in his mind, to seek innovation starting from his analysis, to collect information in his field, to use it in a special program. It is determined by being able to apply it to the process of education and upbringing. [4]

Creativity is a thinking ability, an approach to any life process. By definition, creativity is creative competence in everyday life: at work, in relationships, in studies, and in enriching one's mind. The word creativity can be applied not only to creative people: painters, musicians, directors, actors, writers, but also to doctors.

Self-improvement and self-expression of each student of a medical higher education organization is directly related to his creativity.

In the modern concept of education, the educational process is focused on the student, who has become an active subject of the cognitive process. To achieve the goal, the content of educational programs and teaching technologies will be updated accordingly. Our observations show that each student has a unique individual approach to learning pedagogical subjects.

The process of individual teaching allows teachers to imagine the educational and cognitive activity of students. For example, an important aspect of multimedia technologies is the ability to use various types of information in an integrated form. In addition to traditional teaching aids in the form of tables, texts and pictures, speech aids, music and various animations are used. Providing audio and visual information to students in parallel plays an important role. With the help of computer technologies, students reach a new level of communication. Computer users move easily from one object to another and are able to perceive a sequence of basic concepts. Technologies that help improve student performance and creative thinking belong to hyper-media technologies. They share many of the same qualities as multimedia. It is convenient to use this technology when working on text, because you can easily indicate the necessary words and phrases or enter phrases.

Interactive methods of teaching allow the teacher to exchange ideas with students and implement the principles of individual teaching. The reproductive abilities of students are easily determined by tests. This process can be fully automated. Practical tasks help to determine the level of reproductive abilities of students. It is appropriate to emphasize the creation of an educational environment, which is reflected in the structure of educational materials. For example, typical charts and graphs can show the logical connections between concepts, or it can be a set of questions to ask students.

Their use enriches students' reproductive and production skills. Learning materials should be offered to students in stages based on their content and the requirements of state educational

standards. In order to master the course, each student requires in-depth knowledge, application of creative abilities and independent research. The use of interactive technologies in the educational process gives the teacher a new status when he becomes the manager of the educational process, ready to help the student when there is enough time for active communication with students. During the course study, the teacher consults with the students individually and influences the supervision to successfully promote the student to the intended results.

Interactive technologies include group and team work, joint activities in the form of cooperation. In such conditions, students feel a high level of responsibility for mastering the lesson. Each form of interactive teaching requires the use of a certain technology, in particular: (a) forms such as "microphone", "brainstorming", "piece of speech" are used in frontal types of work; b) methods used in joint work include "face-to-face", "work in pairs and together", "work in small groups", "aquarium"; (c) interactive games ("role playing", "scenario", "court session", etc.); (d) discussion-based technologies ("my point of view" etc.).

Pedagogical teachers of higher education organizations have the opportunity to improve their creative abilities, taking into account the individual characteristics and abilities of students, by using the above interactive teaching methods and technologies together or separately.

Interactive teaching methods and technologies help to create a creative pedagogical environment. They help students acquire theoretical knowledge and practical experience, form students' critical thinking and objective assessment of pedagogical knowledge and events. As a result, students can achieve their individual creative abilities.

Interactive educational situations should be organized in such a way that students should have a clear idea of pedagogical technologies that help to solve emerging problems, as well as mastering new knowledge. Students develop their own ideas and approaches to solving pedagogical tasks in the process of working in a cooperative environment.

Pedagogical teacher interactive education in higher education organizations is important in awakening the interest and creative thinking of students. The main scientific sources for the development of the personality of the future specialist are the researches and publications of psychologists, pedagogues and philosophers. While acquiring scientific knowledge, students engage in interpersonal relationships and learn human values.

From a philosophical point of view, interpersonal relations are established on the basis of equality and cooperation. Participants change and develop in the conditions of cooperation. Based on the humanistic principles of mutual equality and communication, cooperation is shown as the best of the educational process.

Interactive education helps to improve the independence of students, and it is reflected in the personal attitude of future professionals to new information, successful assimilation of professional experience.

Improving the professional potential of students, in general, indicates the use of methods of increasing higher pedagogical culture. Since students act as full-fledged subjects in interactive education, it is appropriate to make full use of improvisation techniques as a method to help ensure a creative pedagogical environment. Interactive education synthesizes a set of techniques, methods and approaches aimed at organizing and improving the educational process, but their application is evaluated by certain requirements:

(a) organization of interactive education and control of its quality and results . taking into account the needs, interests and unique characteristics of students;

(b) cooperation between students and teachers should be implemented at all stages of the interactive learning process;

(v) it is necessary to create conditions for students to acquire the necessary professional competencies, to bring out their activity, initiative, and creativity;

(d) the process of interactive education should be brought closer to the professional activity of future teachers; students should be directed to actively use interactive teaching methods in their future pedagogical activities;

(e) the process of training future teachers includes providing them with professional competencies and especially self-improvement skills.[5]

In conclusion, it can be said that abandoning pre-planning of educational activities, improvement and improvement of creative abilities in future doctors, forcing them to think creatively, come up with new ideas, and improve the attitude to education. change is a key factor in motivating them to achieve.

It is necessary for the teacher not only to use modern information and communication technologies, innovative pedagogical technologies, but also to organize lessons in the spirit of creativity and creative abilities, to use new creative ideas in the educational process.

Based on the above ideas, innovative pedagogical processes aimed at improving the creative abilities of future doctors allow to achieve the intended pedagogical goals.

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